

USING GAMING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE CONTEXT OF AN INTERCULTURAL APPROACH OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14185211>

Berdiyeva Yulduz Turdialiyevna

Lecturer of the department of foreign languages, Journalism and Mass
Communication University of Uzbekistan.

ABSTRACT

The focus of the paper is on educational gaming technologies and how they might be used in foreign language instruction and impact them on intercultural communication among learners. The purposes and benefits of using games as a training tool for foreign languages in the classroom are discussed. Special consideration is given to the categorization of speech and language games. The authors suggest a classification scheme that centers on creative and role-playing games in foreign language instruction, based on an examination of current categories.

Key words: *communicative competence, challenging, encouraging, prone, utilizing, inculcate, disputes, temperaments, competitive aspects*

In order to attain mutual understanding between partners, communication is a social process that involves transferring information of various kinds and contents. It is carried out in compliance with laws and regulations and is purposely delivered through a variety of media. [Sadokhin, 2005] People in the current world are more and more required to communicate and work together with representatives of other nations. However, people cannot think alike or have similar perspectives if they live in different parts of the world. Misunderstandings lead to disputes and occasionally even wars. When G. Treyger and E. Hall's study "Culture and communication" was published in 1954, the term "intercultural competence" entered the scientific discourse. An analysis model. Due to a significant economic shift and the growing need to fortify diplomatic and cross-cultural ties with other nations, it gained traction in Russia in the 1990s. However, the earlier approaches to teaching foreign languages were insufficiently successful. The grammar-translation method, which focuses solely on vocabulary and grammar knowledge, does not equip language learners with information about the customs, etiquette, and culture of the nation where the language is being studied—among the many other essentials for perfect language proficiency. Three key components make up intercultural competence: mastery, which enables pupils to communicate in a language that a foreigner can understand.

Both general and culturally specialized knowledge are the key ones. Naturally, someone who needs to comprehend the people of another nation must be aware of that nation's accomplishments, culture, and history in addition to having a general understanding of other nations' ways of life.

This kind of knowledge, which comes from conversation, is usually helpful in unanticipated circumstances. Second, it's critical to possess strong communication abilities. The key idea is that various temperaments manifest themselves in different ways when communicating. Melancholic and phlegmatic people—those who are prone to internal experiences and communication with oneself—may find it difficult to achieve the goal of the communicative act, whereas choleric and sanguine people, with their quick thinking and resourcefulness, can navigate situations and find solutions to problems with ease and speed. Anybody can experience challenges like a language barrier brought on the fear of making a mistake. Issues in a person's ability to perceive and understand another person may come up during communication. It does not exclude different disputes, from which you must be able to appropriately navigate by seeking a solution. Lastly, the dread of speaking in front of an audience is something that many people have experienced. Teachers of foreign languages should inculcate in their pupils the confidence to communicate. As a result, more than anything else, the learning process needs to be communicative in nature. Learners of foreign languages ought to cultivate intercultural psychological sensitivity. A person without good cause is frequently prone to exalt his culture and believe it to be superior to other cultures. Ethnocentrism can make learning a new language extremely challenging, in addition to being an indication of a poor upbringing. It is evidently incorrect to judge others based entirely on one's own culture since, under the assumption that one's own culture is the only authentic one, this leads to a person acting negatively toward the other person from the outset of conversation.

Unfortunately, for these individuals, their original culture serves as both a barrier isolating them from other people and cultures and a shield preserving their national identity. Consequently, fostering in the next generation a sense of tolerance and respect for the history and customs of all peoples is one of the primary responsibilities of a modern teacher. Students can further avoid the majority of intercultural communication issues if teachers adopt the proper approach to the development of intercultural competence.

A game is a unique human activity that serves as a child's introduction to the world and culture around them. The game promotes self-realization, self-affirmation, and higher self-esteem in addition to helping to showcase a person's skills and abilities. K. D. Ushinsky, a Russian educator who established scientific education in Russia, stated: The characteristics of the game are:

1. Entertaining: The primary goal of the game is to provide amusement, enjoyment, and pique interest in the process of learning;
2. Communicative: enhances one's ability to communicate;
3. Encouraging – guarantees students' self-realization in particular gaming scenarios;
4. Game therapy: it assists students in overcoming challenges that they might face in other kinds of life activities;
5. Diagnostic: this gives pupils self-awareness and enables you to spot departures from standard behavior;
6. Correction function: enhances perception, attention, memory, intelligence, and observation;
7. Intercultural communication: shapes societal values; 6. Positively impacts personality development;
8. Socialization: This process makes sure that values, social conventions, and behavioral patterns are assimilated so that an individual may successfully operate in society [Meshcheryakov, Zinchenko, 2004].

One of the most crucial elements of teaching is the game. N.A.Shcherbakova asserts that fostering a positive environment in the classroom and placing students in successful situations improve learning outcomes and help students get over their shyness, which prevents them from speaking freely in a foreign language [Shcherbakova, 2018]. A teacher wants to develop a linguistic personality that would enable her to become a cultural mediator without sacrificing her own cultural identity. Teaching foreign languages should be focused at the practical application of skills, that is, communicative competence should be established, which involves attaining the goal of a communication act in any scenario. Thus, pedagogical approaches like role-playing games, business simulation, biographical reflection, projects, and so on have a unique place in teaching foreign languages [Galskova, 2004].

Technologies used in gaming might vary. Let's name some of them.

- Discussions in a playful style;
- Games with a competitive component;
- Games employing actual poems, fairy tales and music;
- Games with props;
- Outdoor games.

In addition to adding variety, excitement, and motivation to the language learning process, games also make it easier for pupils to comprehend the cultural nuances of the nation where the language is being learned. In the next chapter, I'll go into more depth about using game approaches in the context of teaching English to people from different cultural backgrounds. Now let's look at an explanation of a few

types of educational gaming activities. Cooperative and competitive aspects are combined in imitation games. By playing this game, players can assess their teamwork abilities as well as their analytical, leadership, and other business skills. Transforming a learner into a character and having them act out the prescribed game activity is the essence of a role-playing game. In these kinds of games, the process of transformation—that is, learning to see the world from another person's perspective—is precisely the most important educational lesson. A business game's pedagogical and didactic significance is in its ability to help participants discover who they are, learn how to take an active role in life, and make decisions about their future careers. Understanding one's own background, clarifying the tenets of one's identity, examining how it manifests in daily life, and drawing comparisons with the lives of peers overseas are all components of biographical reflection. There are many opportunities to integrate the intellectual and emotional aspects of learning in the classroom when different kinds of games are used. Using them enables, among other things, compensating for the overwhelming amount of information that pupils are exposed to and setting up a psychological unloading process for them, both of which improve knowledge assimilation and communication abilities. Games let you set high standards for your own credentials as a teacher while also fostering a creative and laid-back environment in the classroom and teaching strategies for particular communication scenarios. The growth of all cognitive processes—including attention, memory, thinking, and imagination—is impacted by gaming. The primary challenge in learning a foreign language is that students are not immersed in the language. As a result, the instructor must simulate this setting and provide an example of communicating in a foreign language throughout the course. Incorporating gaming activities into the educational process empowers, inspires, and encourages students to delve further into the cultures of other nations. Simultaneously, students acquire the skills to locate pertinent data, modify it, and create strategies based on it to resolve any challenging cross-cultural communication scenario. Additionally, during the game, linguistic barriers such as stereotypes, intercultural shock, prejudices, and fear of making mistakes in oral speaking are addressed. The kids' speech gets richer and more fluid, and their vocabulary grows.

Psychologists from both home and abroad, including J. Piaget, F. Frebel, Z. M. Istomina, R. I. Zhukovskaya, I. A. Zimnyaya, E. I. Negnevitskaya, and L. S. Vygotsky, have noted that the game is This is the best way to teach the target language's culture in that country. The game helps kids develop a positive attitude toward the world around them and stimulates their attention, thinking, and memory. The best classes to increase intercultural competency are those that mimic scenarios that would occur to a visitor from another nation on a vacation or excursion. Quizzes,

tournaments, and role-playing games are helpful. When using game approaches, students become more cognitively independent than when using traditional methods; they go from seeing the subject as an object of learning to seeing it as a subject of activity and communication. Apart from role-playing games, other games that follow rules, creative games like construction games, dramatization, and so on are also utilized. Every lesson needs to be carefully thought out, have a distinct storyline, and include activities that are relevant to the session's goal. Students' cognitive activity thus reaches its peak effectiveness. Additional strategies to guarantee the highest level of student engagement during the lesson include:

- encouraging students to complete tasks;
- utilizing different speech activities, such as dialogue, monologue, and polylogue;
- employing visual aids and theatricalization;
- inundating the content with new vocabulary;
- utilizing different types of cognitive activities (group, team, pair, etc.);
- differentiating instruction for each student;
- creating a welcoming and imaginative environment in the classroom.

As a result, each student action during the class needs to be directed toward communicating the session's goal: • It's not enough to simply modify the wording of the congrats; instead, create cards and place them in envelopes. • It's also important to try interviewing the star as a correspondent in addition to asking questions about the subject.

Teaching a foreign language requires the development of a secondary linguistic personality, which entails teaching students to have a cautious attitude toward a foreign language and to see it as an integral part of culture, in addition to mastering methods and techniques for learning about another nation.

Playing games can help with mental development since they stimulate different parts of the brain. Using game scenarios in the classroom improves student understanding and sparks their curiosity about the subject, which aids in their assimilation of difficult content.

To sum up, games boost students' performance and relieve mental strain and exhaustion. As a result, the game is a useful tool for raising the standard and output of foreign language instruction. Utilizing a variety of games produces positive outcomes and enables pupils to focus on the main objective, which is to master speech abilities in authentic conversational settings. Incorporating gaming activities into the educational process empowers, inspires, and encourages students to delve further into the cultures of other nations. Simultaneously, students acquire the skills to locate pertinent data, modify it, and create strategies based on it to resolve any challenging cross-cultural communication scenario. Furthermore, during the game,

linguistic barriers are eliminated as players overcome culturally shock and their anxiety of making mistakes when speaking aloud. As students' vocabulary grows, so does the richness and freedom of expression.

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